

Reaction of rice varieties or cultures to bacterial blight disease.

Variety or culture	Disease severity scale ^a					
	Seedling		Tillering		Boot-leaf	
	Pots	Field	Pots	Field	Pots	Field
BJ1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sigadis	0	0	0	0	1	0
TKM6	1	0	1	0	1	1
ASD5	1	0	1	1	5	5
IR22	1	1	5	3	5	5
IR26	3	1	5	5	5	5
Pankaj	1	1	3	1	3	3
TNI	5	5	7	7	7	7
TNAU7124 (ASD5/IR22)	1	1	1	1	5	3
TNAU15776 (IR20/ASD5)	1	1	1	1	5	3
ASDIS (IR22/IR26)	3	3	7	1	7	7

^a0 = not affected, 9 = highly susceptible.

tribution of resistance by IR22 and IR20 in those two cultivars appears insufficient. ASD15 (IR22/IR26) is also susceptible (see table).

ASD5 has potential resistance until

the tillering stage to the bacterium strain that causes severe damage to most of the improved rice varieties that are known to be bacterial blight resistant. ■

Root knot nematode—*Fusarium* complex in rice under dryland conditions in Brazil

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A root disease complex is affecting rice in the savannas (cerrados) of the states of Goias, Mato Grosso do Sul, and Mato Grosso where dryland rice is extensively grown.

The symptoms on the aboveground parts were retarded growth, reduced tillering, and pale yellow leaves. The symptoms were evident about 25 days after planting and the difference in height between diseased and healthy plants increased with time.

The affected farmers' fields showed light yellow patches of plants exhibiting retarded growth, and some nutritional disorder was generally suspected. But when the plants were pulled out, a black discoloration was seen at the underground basal node where adventitious roots are initiated. This discoloration extended along the mesocotyl, but seldom to the adventitious roots. Examination of transverse sections of the root at the underground basal node of the culm showed discoloration of vascular tissues. Death of the affected plants was,

however, uncommon.

Isolating more than 50 diseased plant samples from different fields yielded 2 distinct species of *Fusarium*. Inoculation tests using diverse isolates showed that one of the two species was highly

pathogenic. The identification of the pathogenic species is under way.

The incidence of root knot nematode caused by *Meloidogyne javanica* was observed after 75 days of crop growth in the experimental plots at the National Center of Rice and Beans, as well as in some of the farmers' fields affected with *Fusarium*.

Preliminary evaluation of the field incidence in 12 dryland rice cultivars, each grown in plots of 900 m², showed significant differences in the percentage of plants affected by root infection caused by *Fusarium*, root knot nematode, and both root knot and *Fusarium* (see table). While the plants showing galls and egg masses on the roots incited by *M. javanica* had no symptom on the aerial parts, the plants affected with *Fusarium* infection singly or in combination with root knot nematode were retarded in growth and had few tillers.

The root disease complex was commonly found in the second and third year of successive rice cultivations in savannas or in fields where rice is grown in rotation with pasture. ■

Incidence of *Meloidogyne javanica* and *Fusarium* sp. in 12 rice cultivars under upland conditions in Brazil.

Cultivar	Total number of plants	Infected plants ^a (%)	
		<i>Fusarium</i> sp.	<i>M. javanica</i>
Early maturing			
Pratao Precoce (standard)	518	93.71	35.99
Dourado Precoce	402	81.79**	3.49**
IAC 25	303	66.78**	27.31
Medium duration			
IAC 47 (standard)	365	69.86	43.12
Pratao	434	56.32**	40.38
IAC 1246	385	53.18**	38.46
Iguape Redondo	428	46.91**	44.49
Fernandes	294	43.21**	38.67
Amarelao	270	37.23**	62.20**
IAC 5544	312	32.27**	48.27
IRAT 13	261	31.62**	55.77
Bico Ganga	305	29.72**	33.66

^aData presented include combined infection of *Fusarium* and *Meloidogyne*. Mean percentages marked with asterisks are significantly different from the standard checks as judged by t-test at the 1% level of probability.

Evaluation of resistance to rice blast in observation plots of Bagua

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Materials selected from rice blast infection beds were tested for resistance to leaf blast (seedling stage) and neck blast (adult stage) in 20-m² observation plots in fields where the incidence of blast was high. Additional information was taken